

PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING OF COMMUNICATION SERVICES

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Annotation.

The article describes the issues of proper organization of accounting in communication enterprises, correct formalization of the operations that take place in them.

Key words.

communication services, accounting, information services, audit activities, documentation.

Аннотация.

В статье рассмотрены вопросы правильной организации бухгалтерского учета на предприятиях связи, правильного оформления операций, которые в них происходят.

Ключевые слова.

услуги связи, бухгалтерский учет, информационные услуги, аудиторская деятельность, документация.

In the world, the field of communication is recognized as an important "locomotive" of socio-economic development. According to the sources, "50% of the benefits of increasing labor productivity in the countries of the Council of Europe are achieved due to communication; a 10% increase in investment in Internet services leads to an increase in gross domestic product (GDP) by 1-2%; By the beginning of 2020, more than 4.5 billion people worldwide use the Internet, more than 3.8 billion people access social networks, more than 5.19 billion people have mobile phones ; 53% of Internet accesses are made through mobile phones, 44% through personal computers; 64% of Britons do their shopping online through mobile communication ²⁵³. As it can be seen from this case, the improvement of segmental accounting and auditing of communication services in the world today

²⁵³ИКТ-компетентисии как factor sotsialno-ekonomicheskogo razvitiya Rossii / Pod ed. Yu. E. Khokhlova, S. B. Shaposhnika . M.: Institut razvitiya informatsionnogo obshchestva, 2012. - 74 p.; Style and modern economy. M.: IMEMO RAN, 2010. 42 p.; ICTDataandStatistics . InternationalTelecommunicationUnion [Electronic resource]. – The mode is available at: <http://www.itu.int/ITU-D/ict/statistics/>; UnctadStat – StatisticalDatabase [Electronic resource]. – The regime is available at: <http://unctadstat.unctad.org/ReportFolders/reportFolders.aspx> <https://www.web-canape.ru/business/internet-2020-globalnaya-statistika-i-trendy/>

is a very urgent issue.

Today, communication and information services in our republic are wide-ranging and include mail, mobile phone services, television and radio broadcasting, Internet and other types of services. A large number of entities of various statuses and forms of ownership, specializing in communication and information services, are operating in our republic. The increasing demand for communication and information services puts on the agenda the urgent tasks of further improving the activities of the entities specializing in them, improving the quality and service of the provided services, increasing the efficiency of the entities specializing in this field, increasing the income that allows this, optimizing the costs, and reducing the cost. Fulfillment of these important tasks requires conducting in-depth research aimed at further improvement of all management levers in the field of communication and information services, such as the theoretical and methodological foundations of accounting and auditing. The actual aspects of the accounting and auditing of communication and information services in the current conditions, especially the calculation of the income and expenses received from them, the calculation of the cost of the services provided, the indicators of the effectiveness of these services and the factors that have a positive and negative effect on them, further the theoretical, organizational and methodological foundations of the audit analysis. improvement is important.

improving accounting and auditing in entities providing communication and information services have not been researched at the level of special dissertations in our republic. Also, they are not reflected in textbooks, educational and practical manuals. In the years of independence in our republic, some regulatory documents on accounting were adopted in the field of communication and information services, such as postal communication, mobile communication services. However, these normative documents did not embody all the accounting issues of the activity of communication and information services entities. Regulatory documents defining the general procedures of accounting, such as "Regulation on the structure of costs of production and sale of products (work, services) and the formation of financial results", BHMS No. 21 "Financial and economic activities of economic²⁵⁴entities, accounting, plan of accounts" and the instruction on its application"²⁵⁵did not fully cover the characteristics of the subjects of communication and information services. Some practical manuals on the accounting and taxation of

²⁵⁴ Uzbekistan Republic Ministers Decision No. 54 of February 5, 1999 with confirmed (next addition and changes with)

²⁵⁵ Own . Justice ministry by on October 23, 2002 to the list received, No. 1181

foreign communication service entities, such as mobile operators, are ²⁵⁶covered based on the characteristics of the accounting and tax systems of these countries. Based on these sources, it is not without benefits for our republic to study the experiences of foreign countries in establishing accounting services in the field of communication and information services.

We have developed the following suggestions for improving accounting and auditing of communication and information services.

1. Improvement of the theoretical foundations of accounting for communication and information services. It is necessary to reveal the nature and characteristics of communication and information services as accounting and audit objects, based on these characteristics, their classification and descriptive bases should be created.

2. Improvement of the methodological bases of calculation of special types of communication and information services. Improving the procedures for documenting and accounting for mail, mobile communications, broadcasting and Internet services, as well as their cost determination.

3. Creation of methodological bases of audit of communication and information services . In particular, to develop a system of quantitative and qualitative indicators used in auditing the activities of entities providing communication and information services , and ways to assess and determine their reality.

The above proposals will help to further improve the theoretical, organizational and methodological foundations of accounting and auditing in entities that provide communication and information services. They create an opportunity to increase the quality and efficiency of services provided in the field of communication and information, to improve management tools, accounting, reporting, audit and analysis.

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